

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Report on Milestone 23

Usability test of internal data release of one biomedical data set linked to survey data

Dissemination Level	PU
Due Date of Milestone	28/02/2022, M38
Actual Achievement Date	20/01/2022, M37
Lead Beneficiary/LTP	3. SHARE ERIC
Work Package	WP 5 - Innovations in Data Access
Task	Task 5.1 Legal, ethical and technological issues of access to biomedical data
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.4

Abstract:

Milestone 23 documents the test release of the aggregated accelerometer data collected in SHARE. A test release – distributed internally in the SHARE team – was carried out to prepare and evaluate all procedures needed for the scientific release, especially data processing and documentation of the dataset. This is to ensure the data and documentation comply with FAIR principles in making the data accessible and interoperable.

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History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
0.1	04/01/22	First draft	Fabio Franzese
0.2	07/01/22	Revision	Kalina Georgieva
1.0	19/01/22	Final edits and submission	Fabio Franzese

1. Introduction

In its eighth wave the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) measured the physical activity of a sub-sample of respondents with accelerometers (Bergmann & Börsch-Supan, 2021). Measures of physical activity based on acceleration sensors are more reliable and comparable than self-reported assessments of activity (Gupta et al., 2017; cf. Prince et al., 2008). However, the raw data that is recorded by these sensors can only be interpreted after elaborated procedures. To make the accelerometer measurements accessible to researchers from all disciplines, SHARE aims to process the raw data, compute metrics, and provide datasets that are available in an understandable format and thoroughly documented, thus complying with FAIR principles.

2. Description of the Milestone

2.1 Role of the Milestone

The goal of Task 5.1 - Legal, ethical and technological issues of access to biomedical data is to tackle legal, ethical and technological issues of access to biomedical data. After taking care of legal and ethical issues (D5.1) and assuring data access according to FAIR principles (D5.2 & D5.3), this report is a step towards the actual release of the data (D5.4)

In the SHARE accelerometer study, respondents wear an accelerometer on the thigh for eight consecutive days. The data recorded by the device are high frequency raw sensor data that are large and do not have a format that is commonly used by SSH researchers. Therefore, the aim is to process the raw data and provide aggregated, understandable data to SHARE users in a “generated module”.

Prior to the scientific release of these data, a preliminary version of the generated module was distributed in the SHARE team. This internal data release was meant to test data processing, structure, content, and documentation of the generated module. MS23 is the report of the test release and documents its impact on the actual release.

2.2 Means of verification

“Release 0” – the first version of wave 8 SHARE data – was distributed among the SHARE collaborators in October 2020. This internal release comprised a dataset of aggregated measures based on the accelerometer measurements, a so-called generated module. The structure of this dataset differed from the logic of other SHARE datasets: Instead of having one line per respondent, the generated module contained several lines per respondent – one line per day of accelerometer measurement. Not only structure, but also content was new to the SHARE data. Based on the raw sensor data some indicators for physical activity were calculated with GGIR (Migueles, Rowlands, Huber, Sabia, & van Hees, 2019), an open access software. To explain the SHARE accelerometer study as well as the dataset

a documentation was provided. Using the test release, a few research projects were started to explore the aggregated accelerometer measurements (e.g., a mediation analysis on the correlation of physical activity and depressive symptoms). The first users of the generated module commented on the content of the dataset, e.g. which additional information they would like to be included. We also gratefully received feedback from colleagues that identified needs for improvement in the documentation.

3. Conclusions and next steps

The early preparation of Release 0 has helped us to revise the whole procedure of data processing and documentation. The test release was successful as we learned from users which information should be included in the dataset. This gave us the opportunity to extend and improve our data processing procedure. Additionally, we received valuable feedback that resulted in improvements in the documentation. All feedback and insights of the test release affected the next steps towards the scientific release that is issue of D5.4.

4. References

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